

PRODUCTION OF ELECTRIC CARS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article analyzes the possibilities of the production of electric cars in Uzbekistan, the existing problems in the establishment of this industry, shortcomings and their solutions, the current situation in developed countries for the production of electric cars, advanced auto concerns, their achievements and disadvantages.

Keywords: battery, inverter, battery, electric converter,

The popularity of electric cars in the world market is due to their environmental friendliness and fuel economy. Recently, the market for electric vehicles has been expanding rapidly even in our country. Electric cars are gaining popularity in Uzbekistan for several reasons: For electric cars, the duty is not paid, which makes them the best option to buy a modern car at a good price.

The price of gasoline is high, and powering an electric car is much cheaper. Of course, the Tesla brand comes to mind first when it comes to electric cars. But since we are dominated by electric car models under the Chinese brand, it is they that we will consider in this article. To make your choice easier, as of 2024, we have prepared a list of prices for popular electric car models in our country and information about the methods of their purchase. Ways to buy new electric cars In Uzbekistan, a new electric car can be purchased in several ways.

A localized electric car must be purchased from its official dealer. Currently, by such a method, only the BYD brand can be purchased in all regions. Dealer salons can help with model selection tips, credit and insurance. Official dealer BYD electric cars are guaranteed 5 years or 150,000 km for a lithium-ion battery and 3 years or 100,000 km for non-electric parts. More details about the warranty can be found on the company's official website. Buying an electric car from salons where there is no official dealer. Prices in the salon are usually higher than when buying by pre-order. Also, unlike the warranty that the official dealer offers, depending on the type of salon, another salon warranty may be less or not at all. Ordering car delivery from China. Delivery is usually done using the CIP (Carriage and insurance paid to) method. This is a customs procedure that allows the import of goods without prior payment of customs duties and

taxes. CIP can be purchased from companies specializing in the import of electric vehicles. Some car dealerships also provide CIP services.

BYD Seagull Compact electric hatchback developed by the BYD Company. The Model will be produced as an affordable electric car since 2023. As of may 2024, there are 445 announcements on sales of this electric car model on the Olx platform, and 78 on the Autoelon.

This car is equipped with a front-wheel drive privod. Engine power is 75 hp, acceleration from 0 to 100 km/h is 13.5 seconds. The range is from 305 to 405 kilometers, depending on the battery capacity. The charging time is 6-8 hours from the household outlet, and from the charging station up to 80% in 30 minutes. Power consumption ranges from 12.5 to 14.3 kW per 100 km.

The maximum speed of the car is 130 km / h. In terms of dimensions, the length of the car is 3780 mm, the width is 1670 mm, the height is 1560 mm, the wheel base is 2510 mm. The Salon has five seats, and the luggage capacity is 245 liters. The car weighs 1160 kg. Pros Affordable price: one of the cheapest electric vehicles on the market. Spacious interior: despite its compact size, The Seagull has enough space for up to five people. Practical design: compact size, convenient for the city. There are not many power costs. The main set contains all the necessary functions, such as air conditioning, electronic windows and a multimedia system. Disadvantages Power is relatively low, and maximum speed is also limited: 130 km / h, which may not be enough for some drivers.

BYD Yuan plus Is a subcompact crossover produced by BYD named in honor of the Yuan dynasty of Chinese emperors. As of may 2024, there are 218 announcements on sales of this electric car model on the Olx platform, and 43 on the Autoelon. This car can be front or all-wheel drive (AWD).

Engine power ranges from 200 to 300 hp, acceleration from 0 to 100 km/h from 7.9 to 10.6 seconds. The power reserve is from 400 to 510 kilometers. The battery capacity is from 56.3 to 76.9 kWh. The maximum speed of the car is from 160 to 180 km / h. In terms of dimensions: length 4585 mm, width 1875 mm and height 1680 mm, and wheelbase 2720 mm. The Salon is designed for five people, and the luggage capacity is from 523 to 1650 liters. Weight ranges from 1,615 to 1,690 kg. Pros Beautiful and stylish design, smooth body, LED headlights, panoramic roof. Spacious lounge: comfortable seats, plenty of space for passengers and luggage. Modern equipment: digital instrument panel, multimedia touch screen, driver assistance systems.

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